

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CHILD EDUCATION IN THE FAMILY

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Annotation: *this article provides information about the upbringing of a child in the family, the opinions of great thinkers scientists about the family, and family relationships.*

Key words: *Family, upbringing, thoughts of Abu Ali ibn Sina, "Qabusnami" of Caicavus aggression.*

Family is the foundation of maturation. Family-a hearth of upbringing. Family is the basis of society. It is the environment in which ideological and spiritual education is carried out, in which all human qualities, noble intentions, conspiracies, values are found in each person, which are shaped in his mind from an early age. The Uzbek family is such a place where our centuries-old strong spiritual values have developed that its stability and strength are one of the important factors in the development of our society. About this president I.A.In the work " High spirituality – invincible power " Karimov writes: no doubt in shaping and exalting the specific spirituality of any nation, the role and influence of the family is incomparable. Because the purest and purest feelings of a person, the first Life concept and founders are formed in the family at the first time. If the atmosphere in the family is healthy, then the younger generation, having matured, will be able to show noble features to the soul and soul, national and universal values, the idea of national independence

A lot of scientists have commented on the family, in particular, the pedagogical and psychological views of Abu Ali ibn Sina were built on a social basis, which advocated the use of a universal principle in raising a child, and the educator instructed parents that it is better to raise a child through a personal lesson than through severe bodily punishment. In matters of moral education, alloma emphasized the place of the family. The issue of family and family relations is described in its own way in the work " event address". In addition, the " Cabusnoma " of Kaykowus is considered to be such rare works on upbringing. The opinions and instructions contained in it are an important program for parents, especially

in the upbringing of young men and girls of teenage and adolescent age. This book calls on young people to respect, honor parents. His thoughts on this matter are set forth in the chapter of the pandnoma "to know the truth of the parents": "every child, if he is wise and wise, is a parent, loving

It seems that girls who ignored their mothers in childhood and did not receive the necessary affection from their parents would tend to punish their children and scatter their aggression on them in most cases when they were mothers themselves. Although such conclusions are not fully recognized, but draw attention as conclusions based on the indicators of the results of the study conducted by foreign psychologists. It is appropriate to express the following considerations as the presence of different aspects in our Uzbek mentality from abroad. In the Uzbek environment, too, there are divorces who do not feed on unfriendly families or parental love, but one of the great aspects of uzbekism is that this kenticity in the heart of a child is not caused by the love of others (grandparents, neighbourhoods) and by the childish policies pursued by our country, it does not cause such negative vices as abroad.

In conclusion, it can be said that the family plays an important role in raising a child. And the conditions in the family give rise to various psychological characteristics in the child. The relationship between parents has a huge impact on the child. Because the child often tries to resemble his parents and takes an example from them, as a clear example of which the opinion of the above scientists is the basis. Family is a small community within society, and family peace is the foundation of the future for the peace of the country, the health and upbringing of children. That is why it is necessary for parents to be more attentive to raising children, to spend a lot of time together with them, to create conditions for their free time to be productive. In the hands of future youth, so let's not be indifferent to the fate of our children.

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